

Comparison of alternative LCA model specifications with original baseline LCA model

Alternative LCA model specifications	Best class solution (based on BIC)	Class assignments (observations per class)	BIC (by num. of classes: 2, 3, 4, 5, 6)	Simple cross-tabulation (% observations falling into the same class) ^A	Global entropy similarity (correlation of posterior probabilities) ^A	Class-specific entropy similarity (correlation of posterior probabilities) ^A	Adjusted Rand Index ^B
<i>Baseline (original) model</i>	3	Class 1= 77 Class 2= 69 Class 3= 54	3684.878 3593.281 3626.082 3749.811 3812.662	-	-	-	-
<i>model – dropping Q1. Risk attitude</i>	3	Class 1=76 Class 2= 45 Class 3= 79	2876.01 2865.819 2914.797 3022.941 3057.267	96%	0.94	Class 1= 0.93 Class 2= 0.90 Class 3= 0.97	0.88
<i>model - dropping Q2. Innovativeness</i>	2	Class 1= 121 Class 2= 79 Class 3= -	2811.5 2836.208 2826.029 2840.704 2970.137	61%	0.41	Class 1= 0.65 Class 2= -0.16 Class 3= 0.61	0.61
<i>model - dropping Q3. Openness</i>	3	Class 1= 79 Class 2= 96 Class 3= 25	2830.516 2823.597 2842.118 2881.871 2957.439	86%	0.78	Class 1= 0.76 Class 2= 0.63 Class 3= 0.97	0.69
<i>model - dropping Q4. GMO interest</i>	2	Class 1= 79 Class 2= 121 Class 3= -	3424.492 3536.187 3529.878 3603.47 3626.435	73%	0.29	Class 1= 0.55 Class 2= 0.36 Class 3= 0.04	0.61

model - dropping Q5. GE interest	2	Class 1= 69 Class 2= 131 Class 3= -	3507.043 3563.236 3580.545 3604.304 3639.483	55%	0.44	Class 1= 0.52 Class 2= 0.51 Class 3= 0.31	0.22
model - dropping Q6. GE Regulation	3	Class 1= 64 Class 2= 110 Class 3= 26	3043.111 3012.057 3044.802 3121.902 3195.227	60%	0.39	Class 1= 0.65 Class 2= -0.24 Class 3= 0.58	0.43
model - dropping Q7. GE cultivation	2	Class 1= 69 Class 2= 131 Class 3= -	2972.746 3040.015 3053 3103.478 3207.304	45%	0.32	Class 1= 0.34 Class 2= 0.46 Class 3= 0.18	0.22
Simpler model 1 Includes variables: Q1. Risk attitude; Q2. Innovativeness; Q3. Openness; Q4. Q5. GE interest	3	Class 1= 65 Class 2= 42 Class 3= 93	2289.713 2266.656 2310.601 2398.536 2476.528	42%	0.12	Class 1= 0.12 Class 2= 0.20 Class 3= 0.11	0.01
Simpler model 2 Input variables: Q5. GE interest; Q6. GE Regulation; Q7. GE cultivation	6	Class 1= 74 Class 2= 21 Class 3= 15 Class 4= 29 Class 5= 11 Class 6= 50	1187.787 1144.134 1126.675 1110.9 1082.261	45%	0.69	Class 1= 0.87 Class 2= 0.53 Class 3= 0.71	0.65

Note: baseline model includes variables Q1. Risk attitude; Q2. Innovativeness; Q3. Openness; Q4. GMO interest; Q5. GE interest; Q6. GE Regulation; Q7. GE cultivation

A. Comparison is only possible between solutions with same number of classes. Hence, 3-class solutions are compared among models.

B. The index varies from 0 to 1, where 1 means perfect match, and 0 complete difference. By rule of thumb, index between 0.4-0.8 is moderately stable, while > 0.8 shows excellent stability. Comparison of best class solution with different numbers of classes is possible.

Characterisation of alternative LCA solutions

Model 1 (- Q1. Risk attitude)

Variable name	Unit of measure	Whole sample	CLASSES		
			1	2	3
No. of farms		200	76	45	79
CLASSIFIER VARIABLES					
Attitude to innovations					
Risk attitude to innovation risks	mean	5.0	5.1	4.8	5.0
Innovativeness	mean	4.4	4.3	4.4	4.6
Openness to new tech and varieties	mean	4.5	4.4	4.5	4.7
Willingness to adopt GT crops					
GMO crops	% farms	87.5%	97.4	62.2	92.4
gene-edited crops	% farms	91.5%	96.1	73.3	97.5
Preference on gene-editing regulation option					
Follow GM regulation	% farms	8.0%	0.0	24.4	6.3
Follow regulation for traditional crops	% farms	23.5%	0.0	51.1	30.4
Have its own regulation	% farms	65.5%	100.0	11.1	63.3
Preference on gene-edited crops' use					
Should be cultivated	% farms	39.5%	0.0	0.0	100.0
Should be cultivated with restrictions	% farms	55.0%	94.7	84.4	0.0
Should be banned/not cultivated	% farms	5.5%	5.3	15.6	0.0
OTHER VARIABLES ON NGT PREFERENCES					
Preferences on NGT improvements					
Pest/disease resistance	mean	6.0	6.0	6.0	6.1
Herbicides tolerance	mean	5.4	5.3	5.2	5.6
Drought resistance	mean	5.5	5.4	5.3	5.7
Nutrients and water use efficiency	mean	5.6	5.6	5.4	5.7
Adaptation to warmer temperature	mean	5.2	5.2	5.1	5.4
Earlier flowering to anticipate harvest	mean	4.8	4.7	4.6	5.0
Trust in information sources about NGT					
Government	mean	3.8	3.9	3.8	3.7
Mass media	mean	2.5	2.4	2.5	2.6
Social media	mean	2.6	2.7	2.3	2.7
NFU	mean	5.1	5.1	4.9	5.2
Technology providers	mean	4.8	4.8	4.5	5.0
Research institutes	mean	5.8	5.8	5.4	6.1
Neighboring farmers	mean	4.6	4.6	4.7	4.6
Environmental NGOs	mean	3.0	3.0	3.6	2.6
overall trust	mean	4.0	4.0	4.0	4.1
Preference on free-cultivation regime					
Without restriction	% farms	20%	0.0	0.0	50.6
Under regulation like other crops	% farms	36%	0.0	0.0	89.9
Preferences on restrictions					
Minimum distance from other crops	% farms	38%	72.4	44.4	0.0
Use of natural barriers	% farms	30%	51.3	46.7	0.0
Gene-editing labelling	% farms	38%	65.8	57.8	0.0
Tracing gene-edited products	% farms	43%	78.9	57.8	0.0
Mandatory risk assessment	% farms	47%	82.9	68.9	0.0
Preferences on reasons to ban NGT crops					
Consumers do not want them	% farms	3%	1.3	8.9	0.0
Danger to health and environment	% farms	3%	1.3	8.9	0.0
Ruin the image of rural economy	% farms	2%	0.0	8.9	0.0

Model 2 (- Q2. Innovativeness)

Variable name	Unit of measure	Whole sample	CLASSES	
			1	2
No. of farms		200	121	79
CLASSIFIER VARIABLES				
Attitude to innovations				
Risk attitude to innovation risks	mean	5.0	5.0	5.0
Innovativeness	mean	4.4	4.3	4.6
Openness to new tech and varieties	mean	4.5	4.4	4.7
Willingness to adopt GT crops				
GMO crops	% farms	87.5%	84.3	92.4
gene-edited crops	% farms	91.5%	87.6	97.5
Preference on gene-editing regulation option				
Follow GM regulation	% farms	8.0%	9.1	6.3
Follow regulation for traditional crops	% farms	23.5%	19.0	30.4
Have its own regulation	% farms	65.5%	66.9	63.3
Preference on gene-edited crops' use				
Should be cultivated	% farms	39.5%	0.0	100.0
Should be cultivated with restrictions	% farms	55.0%	90.9	0.0
Should be banned/not cultivated	% farms	5.5%	9.1	0.0
OTHER VARIABLES ON NGT PREFERENCES				
Preferences on NGT improvements				
Pest/disease resistance	mean	6.0	6.0	6.1
Herbicides tolerance	mean	5.4	5.3	5.6
Drought resistance	mean	5.5	5.4	5.7
Nutrients and water use efficiency	mean	5.6	5.5	5.7
Adaptation to warmer temperature	mean	5.2	5.1	5.4
Earlier flowering to anticipate harvest	mean	4.8	4.7	5.0
Trust in information sources about NGT				
Government	mean	3.8	3.9	3.7
Mass media	mean	2.5	2.5	2.6
Social media	mean	2.6	2.5	2.7
NFU	mean	5.1	5.0	5.2
Technology providers	mean	4.8	4.7	5.0
Research institutes	mean	5.8	5.7	6.1
Neighboring farmers	mean	4.6	4.6	4.6
Environmental NGOs	mean	3.0	3.2	2.6
overall trust	mean	4.0	4.0	4.1
Preference on free-cultivation regime				
Without restriction	% farms	20%	0.0	50.6
Under regulation like other crops	% farms	36%	0.0	89.9
Preferences on restrictions				
Minimum distance from other crops	% farms	38%	62.0	0.0
Use of natural barriers	% farms	30%	49.6	0.0
Gene-editing labelling	% farms	38%	62.8	0.0
Tracing gene-edited products	% farms	43%	71.1	0.0
Mandatory risk assessment	% farms	47%	77.7	0.0
Preferences on reasons to ban NGT crops				
Consumers do not want them	% farms	3%	4.1322314	0
Danger to health and environment	% farms	3%	4.1322314	0
Ruin the image of rural economy	% farms	2%	3.3057851	0

Model 3 (- Q3. Openness)

Variable name	Unit of measure	Whole sample	CLASSES		
			1	2	3
No. of farms		200	25	79	96
CLASSIFIER VARIABLES					
Attitude to innovations					
Risk attitude to innovation risks	mean	5.0	5.1	5.0	5.0
Innovativeness	mean	4.4	4.1	4.6	4.4
Openness to new tech and varieties	mean	4.5	4.0	4.7	4.5
Willingness to adopt GT crops					
GMO crops	% farms	87.5%	28.0	92.4	99.0
gene-edited crops	% farms	91.5%	44.0	97.5	99.0
Preference on gene-editing regulation option					
Follow GM regulation	% farms	8.0%	12.0	6.3	8.3
Follow regulation for traditional crops	% farms	23.5%	32.0	30.4	15.6
Have its own regulation	% farms	65.5%	44.0	63.3	72.9
Preference on gene-edited crops' use					
Should be cultivated	% farms	39.5%	0.0	100.0	0.0
Should be cultivated with restrictions	% farms	55.0%	56.0	0.0	100.0
Should be banned/not cultivated	% farms	5.5%	44.0	0.0	0.0
OTHER VARIABLES ON NGT PREFERENCES					
Preferences on NGT improvements					
Pest/disease resistance	mean	6.0	5.8	6.1	6.1
Herbicides tolerance	mean	5.4	4.6	5.6	5.5
Drought resistance	mean	5.5	5.0	5.7	5.5
Nutrients and water use efficiency	mean	5.6	4.9	5.7	5.7
Adaptation to warmer temperature	mean	5.2	4.5	5.4	5.3
Earlier flowering to anticipate harvest	mean	4.8	4.6	5.0	4.7
Trust in information sources about NGT					
Government	mean	3.8	3.4	3.7	4.0
Mass media	mean	2.5	2.6	2.6	2.4
Social media	mean	2.6	2.4	2.7	2.6
NFU	mean	5.1	4.6	5.2	5.1
Technology providers	mean	4.8	3.7	5.0	4.9
Research institutes	mean	5.8	5.0	6.1	5.8
Neighboring farmers	mean	4.6	4.4	4.6	4.6
Environmental NGOs	mean	3.0	3.6	2.6	3.1
overall trust	mean	4.0	3.7	4.1	4.1
Preference on free-cultivation regime					
Without restriction	% farms	20%	0.0	50.6	0.0
Under regulation like other crops	% farms	36%	0.0	89.9	0.0
Preferences on restrictions					
Minimum distance from other crops	% farms	38%	28.0	0.0	70.8
Use of natural barriers	% farms	30%	24.0	0.0	56.3
Gene-editing labelling	% farms	38%	40.0	0.0	68.8
Tracing gene-edited products	% farms	43%	48.0	0.0	77.1
Mandatory risk assessment	% farms	47%	60.0	0.0	82.3
Preferences on reasons to ban NGT crops					
Consumers do not want them	% farms	3%	20.0	0.0	0.0
Danger to health and environment	% farms	3%	20.0	0.0	0.0
Ruin the image of rural economy	% farms	2%	16.0	0.0	0.0

Model 4 (- Q4. GMO interest)

Variable name	Unit of measure	Whole sample	CLASSES	
			1	2
No. of farms		200	79	121
CLASSIFIER VARIABLES				
Attitude to innovations				
Risk attitude to innovation risks	mean	5.0	5.0	5.0
Innovativeness	mean	4.4	4.6	4.3
Openness to new tech and varieties	mean	4.5	4.7	4.4
Willingness to adopt GT crops				
GMO crops	% farms	87.5%	92.4	84.3
gene-edited crops	% farms	91.5%	97.5	87.6
Preference on gene-editing regulation option				
Follow GM regulation	% farms	8.0%	6.3	9.1
Follow regulation for traditional crops	% farms	23.5%	30.4	19.0
Have its own regulation	% farms	65.5%	63.3	66.9
Preference on gene-edited crops' use				
Should be cultivated	% farms	39.5%	100.0	0.0
Should be cultivated with restrictions	% farms	55.0%	0.0	90.9
Should be banned/not cultivated	% farms	5.5%	0.0	9.1
OTHER VARIABLES ON NGT PREFERENCES				
Preferences on NGT improvements				
Pest/disease resistance	mean	6.0	6.1	6.0
Herbicides tolerance	mean	5.4	5.6	5.3
Drought resistance	mean	5.5	5.7	5.4
Nutrients and water use efficiency	mean	5.6	5.7	5.5
Adaptation to warmer temperature	mean	5.2	5.4	5.1
Earlier flowering to anticipate harvest	mean	4.8	5.0	4.7
Trust in information sources about NGT				
Government	mean	3.8	3.7	3.9
Mass media	mean	2.5	2.6	2.5
Social media	mean	2.6	2.7	2.5
NFU	mean	5.1	5.2	5.0
Technology providers	mean	4.8	5.0	4.7
Research institutes	mean	5.8	6.1	5.7
Neighboring farmers	mean	4.6	4.6	4.6
Environmental NGOs	mean	3.0	2.6	3.2
overall trust	mean	4.0	4.1	4.0
Preference on free-cultivation regime				
Without restriction	% farms	20%	50.6	0.0
Under regulation like other crops	% farms	36%	89.9	0.0
Preferences on restrictions				
Minimum distance from other crops	% farms	38%	0.0	62.0
Use of natural barriers	% farms	30%	0.0	49.6
Gene-editing labelling	% farms	38%	0.0	62.8
Tracing gene-edited products	% farms	43%	0.0	71.1
Mandatory risk assessment	% farms	47%	0.0	77.7
Preferences on reasons to ban NGT crops				
Consumers do not want them	% farms	3%	0.0	4.1
Danger to health and environment	% farms	3%	0.0	4.1
Ruin the image of rural economy	% farms	2%	0.0	3.3

Model 5 (- Q5. GE interest)

Variable name	Unit of measure	Whole sample	CLASSES	
			1	2
No. of farms		200	69	131
CLASSIFIER VARIABLES				
Attitude to innovations				
Risk attitude to innovation risks	mean	5.0	4.9	5.1
Innovativeness	mean	4.4	4.6	4.4
Openness to new tech and varieties	mean	4.5	4.8	4.4
Willingness to adopt GT crops				
GMO crops	% farms	87.5%	78.3	92.4
gene-edited crops	% farms	91.5%	88.4	93.1
Preference on gene-editing regulation option				
Follow GM regulation	% farms	8.0%	23.2	0.0
Follow regulation for traditional crops	% farms	23.5%	68.1	0.0
Have its own regulation	% farms	65.5%	0.0	100.0
Preference on gene-edited crops' use				
Should be cultivated	% farms	39.5%	42.0	38.2
Should be cultivated with restrictions	% farms	55.0%	52.2	56.5
Should be banned/not cultivated	% farms	5.5%	5.8	5.3
OTHER VARIABLES ON NGT PREFERENCES				
Preferences on NGT improvements				
Pest/disease resistance	mean	6.0	6.1	6.0
Herbicides tolerance	mean	5.4	5.4	5.4
Drought resistance	mean	5.5	5.4	5.6
Nutrients and water use efficiency	mean	5.6	5.4	5.7
Adaptation to warmer temperature	mean	5.2	5.3	5.2
Earlier flowering to anticipate harvest	mean	4.8	4.8	4.8
Trust in information sources about NGT				
Government	mean	3.8	3.7	3.8
Mass media	mean	2.5	2.6	2.5
Social media	mean	2.6	2.6	2.6
NFU	mean	5.1	5.0	5.1
Technology providers	mean	4.8	4.8	4.8
Research institutes	mean	5.8	5.7	5.9
Neighboring farmers	mean	4.6	4.7	4.6
Environmental NGOs	mean	3.0	3.3	2.8
overall trust	mean	4.0	4.1	4.0
Preference on free-cultivation regime				
Without restriction	% farms	20%	27.5	16.0
Under regulation like other crops	% farms	36%	37.7	34.4
Preferences on restrictions				
Minimum distance from other crops	% farms	38%	27.5	42.7
Use of natural barriers	% farms	30%	30.4	29.8
Gene-editing labelling	% farms	38%	36.2	38.9
Tracing gene-edited products	% farms	43%	34.8	47.3
Mandatory risk assessment	% farms	47%	42.0	49.6
Preferences on reasons to ban NGT crops				
Consumers do not want them	% farms	3%	4.3	1.5
Danger to health and environment	% farms	3%	4.3	1.5
Ruin the image of rural economy	% farms	2%	4.3	0.8

Model 6 (- Q6. GE Regulation)

Variable name	Unit of measure	Whole sample	CLASSES		
			1	2	3
No. of farms		200	64	110	26
CLASSIFIER VARIABLES					
Attitude to innovations					
Risk attitude to innovation risks	mean	5.0	5.2	4.9	4.8
Innovativeness	mean	4.4	5.0	4.3	3.5
Openness to new tech and varieties	mean	4.5	5.1	4.5	3.5
Willingness to adopt GT crops					
GMO crops	% farms	87.5%	87.5	87.3	88.5
gene-edited crops	% farms	91.5%	89.1	90.9	100.0
Preference on gene-editing regulation option					
Follow GM regulation	% farms	8.0%	7.8	9.1	3.8
Follow regulation for traditional crops	% farms	23.5%	32.8	19.1	19.2
Have its own regulation	% farms	65.5%	57.8	67.3	76.9
Preference on gene-edited crops' use					
Should be cultivated	% farms	39.5%	82.8	0.0	100.0
Should be cultivated with restrictions	% farms	55.0%	0.0	100.0	0.0
Should be banned/not cultivated	% farms	5.5%	17.2	0.0	0.0
OTHER VARIABLES ON NGT PREFERENCES					
Preferences on NGT improvements					
Pest/disease resistance	mean	6.0	5.9	6.1	6.0
Herbicides tolerance	mean	5.4	5.3	5.4	5.5
Drought resistance	mean	5.5	5.5	5.4	5.8
Nutrients and water use efficiency	mean	5.6	5.6	5.6	5.6
Adaptation to warmer temperature	mean	5.2	5.3	5.2	5.2
Earlier flowering to anticipate harvest	mean	4.8	5.1	4.7	5.0
Trust in information sources about NGT					
Government	mean	3.8	3.5	4.0	3.8
Mass media	mean	2.5	2.7	2.4	2.5
Social media	mean	2.6	2.6	2.6	2.5
NFU	mean	5.1	5.1	5.1	5.0
Technology providers	mean	4.8	4.8	4.8	4.7
Research institutes	mean	5.8	5.7	5.8	5.9
Neighboring farmers	mean	4.6	4.5	4.7	4.5
Environmental NGOs	mean	3.0	3.0	3.2	2.2
overall trust	mean	4.0	4.0	4.1	3.9
Preference on free-cultivation regime					
Without restriction	% farms	20%	46.9	0.0	38.5
Under regulation like other crops	% farms	36%	75.0	0.0	88.5
Preferences on restrictions					
Minimum distance from other crops	% farms	38%	1.6	67.3	0.0
Use of natural barriers	% farms	30%	0.0	54.5	0.0
Gene-editing labelling	% farms	38%	0.0	69.1	0.0
Tracing gene-edited products	% farms	43%	1.6	77.3	0.0
Mandatory risk assessment	% farms	47%	3.1	83.6	0.0
Preferences on reasons to ban NGT crops					
Consumers do not want them	% farms	3%	7.8	0.0	0.0
Danger to health and environment	% farms	3%	7.8	0.0	0.0
Ruin the image of rural economy	% farms	2%	6.3	0.0	0.0

Model 7 (- Q7. GE cultivation)

Variable name	Unit of measure	Whole sample	CLASSES	
			1	2
No. of farms		200	131	69
CLASSIFIER VARIABLES				
Attitude to innovations				
Risk attitude to innovation risks	mean	5.0	5.1	4.9
Innovativeness	mean	4.4	4.4	4.6
Openness to new tech and varieties	mean	4.5	4.4	4.8
Willingness to adopt GT crops				
GMO crops	% farms	87.5%	92.4	78.3
gene-edited crops	% farms	91.5%	93.1	88.4
Preference on gene-editing regulation option				
Follow GM regulation	% farms	8.0%	0.0	23.2
Follow regulation for traditional crops	% farms	23.5%	0.0	68.1
Have its own regulation	% farms	65.5%	100.0	0.0
Preference on gene-edited crops' use				
Should be cultivated	% farms	39.5%	38.2	42.0
Should be cultivated with restrictions	% farms	55.0%	56.5	52.2
Should be banned/not cultivated	% farms	5.5%	5.3	5.8
OTHER VARIABLES ON NGT PREFERENCES				
Preferences on NGT improvements				
Pest/disease resistance	mean	6.0	6.0	6.1
Herbicides tolerance	mean	5.4	5.4	5.4
Drought resistance	mean	5.5	5.6	5.4
Nutrients and water use efficiency	mean	5.6	5.7	5.4
Adaptation to warmer temperature	mean	5.2	5.2	5.3
Earlier flowering to anticipate harvest	mean	4.8	4.8	4.8
Trust in information sources about NGT				
Government	mean	3.8	3.8	3.7
Mass media	mean	2.5	2.5	2.6
Social media	mean	2.6	2.6	2.6
NFU	mean	5.1	5.1	5.0
Technology providers	mean	4.8	4.8	4.8
Research institutes	mean	5.8	5.9	5.7
Neighboring farmers	mean	4.6	4.6	4.7
Environmental NGOs	mean	3.0	2.8	3.3
overall trust	mean	4.0	4.0	4.1
Preference on free-cultivation regime				
Without restriction	% farms	20%	16.0	27.5
Under regulation like other crops	% farms	36%	34.4	37.7
Preferences on restrictions				
Minimum distance from other crops	% farms	38%	42.7	27.5
Use of natural barriers	% farms	30%	29.8	30.4
Gene-editing labelling	% farms	38%	38.9	36.2
Tracing gene-edited products	% farms	43%	47.3	34.8
Mandatory risk assessment	% farms	47%	49.6	42.0
Preferences on reasons to ban NGT crops				
Consumers do not want them	% farms	3%	1.5	4.3
Danger to health and environment	% farms	3%	1.5	4.3
Ruin the image of rural economy	% farms	2%	0.8	4.3

Simpler model 1 (Input variables: Q1. Risk attitude; Q2. Innovativeness; Q3. Openness; Q4. Q5. GE interest)

Variable name	Unit of measure	Whole sample	CLASSES		
			1	2	3
No. of farms		200	65	42	93
CLASSIFIER VARIABLES					
Attitude to innovations					
Risk attitude to innovation risks	mean	5.0	5.2	5.7	4.5
Innovativeness	mean	4.4	5.1	6.0	3.2
Openness to new tech and varieties	mean	4.5	4.9	6.4	3.5
Willingness to adopt GT crops					
GMO crops	% farms	87.5%	98.5	83.3	81.7
gene-edited crops	% farms	91.5%	98.5	90.5	87.1
Preference on gene-editing regulation option					
Follow GM regulation	% farms	8.0%	6.2	7.1	9.7
Follow regulation for traditional crops	% farms	23.5%	21.5	33.3	20.4
Have its own regulation	% farms	65.5%	70.8	57.1	65.6
Preference on gene-edited crops' use					
Should be cultivated	% farms	39.5%	41.5	50.0	33.3
Should be cultivated with restrictions	% farms	55.0%	55.4	45.2	59.1
Should be banned/not cultivated	% farms	5.5%	3.1	4.8	7.5
OTHER VARIABLES ON NGT PREFERENCES					
Preferences on NGT improvements					
Pest/disease resistance	mean	6.0	6.0	6.2	5.9
Herbicides tolerance	mean	5.4	5.4	5.6	5.3
Drought resistance	mean	5.5	5.6	5.6	5.3
Nutrients and water use efficiency	mean	5.6	5.8	6.0	5.3
Adaptation to warmer temperature	mean	5.2	5.3	5.5	5.1
Earlier flowering to anticipate harvest	mean	4.8	4.8	5.0	4.7
Trust in information sources about NGT					
Government	mean	3.8	4.1	3.8	3.6
Mass media	mean	2.5	2.6	2.6	2.4
Social media	mean	2.6	2.9	2.7	2.3
NFU	mean	5.1	5.2	5.2	4.9
Technology providers	mean	4.8	5.0	5.1	4.5
Research institutes	mean	5.8	5.9	6.0	5.6
Neighboring farmers	mean	4.6	4.8	4.6	4.5
Environmental NGOs	mean	3.0	3.0	3.0	2.9
overall trust	mean	4.0	4.2	4.1	3.8
Preference on free-cultivation regime					
Without restriction	% farms	20%	18.5	33.3	15.1
Under regulation like other crops	% farms	36%	38.5	42.9	30.1
Preferences on restrictions					
Minimum distance from other crops	% farms	38%	40.0	35.7	36.6
Use of natural barriers	% farms	30%	27.7	21.4	35.5
Gene-editing labelling	% farms	38%	38.5	33.3	39.8
Tracing gene-edited products	% farms	43%	47.7	33.3	44.1
Mandatory risk assessment	% farms	47%	49.2	40.5	48.4
Preferences on reasons to ban NGT crops					
Consumers do not want them	% farms	3%	3.1	2.4	2.2
Danger to health and environment	% farms	3%	1.5	2.4	3.2
Ruin the image of rural economy	% farms	2%	1.5	2.4	2.2

Simpler model 2 (Input variables: Q5. GE interest; Q6. GE Regulation; Q7. GE cultivation)

Variable name	Unit of measure	Whole sample	CLASSES					
			1	2	3	4	5	6
No. of farms		200	74	21	15	29	11	50
CLASSIFIER VARIABLES								
Attitude to innovations								
Risk attitude to innovation risks	mean	5.0	5.1	5.0	4.1	5.1	5.5	5.0
Innovativeness	mean	4.4	4.3	4.2	4.6	4.6	4.4	4.6
Openness to new tech and varieties	mean	4.5	4.4	4.5	4.7	5.0	4.1	4.6
Willingness to adopt GT crops								
GMO crops	% farms	87.5%	94.6	76.2	66.7	89.7	54.5	94.0
gene-edited crops	% farms	91.5%	94.6	85.7	80.0	100.0	54.5	96.0
Preference on gene-editing regulation option								
Follow GM regulation	% farms	8.0%	0.0	0.0	66.7	17.2	9.1	0.0
Follow regulation for traditional crops	% farms	23.5%	0.0	100.0	0.0	82.8	18.2	0.0
Have its own regulation	% farms	65.5%	100.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	63.6	100.0
Preference on gene-edited crops' use								
Should be cultivated	% farms	39.5%	0.0	0.0	0.0	100.0	0.0	100.0
Should be cultivated with restrictions	% farms	55.0%	100.0	100.0	100.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
Should be banned/not cultivated	% farms	5.5%	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	100.0	0.0
OTHER VARIABLES ON NGT PREFERENCES								
Preferences on NGT improvements								
Pest/disease resistance	mean	6.0	6.0	6.0	6.5	6.0	5.2	6.1
Herbicides tolerance	mean	5.4	5.3	5.4	5.9	5.5	3.9	5.6
Drought resistance	mean	5.5	5.4	5.3	5.5	5.4	5.3	5.9
Nutrients and water use efficiency	mean	5.6	5.6	5.6	5.3	5.6	4.9	5.8
Adaptation to warmer temperature	mean	5.2	5.1	5.4	5.2	5.4	4.8	5.4
Earlier flowering to anticipate harvest	mean	4.8	4.7	4.9	4.4	5.1	5.1	5.0
Trust in information sources about NGT								
Government	mean	3.8	4.0	3.7	4.2	3.6	3.0	3.8
Mass media	mean	2.5	2.4	2.6	2.4	2.7	2.7	2.5
Social media	mean	2.6	2.7	2.0	2.7	3.0	2.2	2.5
NFU	mean	5.1	5.1	4.9	5.4	5.2	3.9	5.2
Technology providers	mean	4.8	4.8	4.6	5.1	5.1	3.1	5.0
Research institutes	mean	5.8	5.9	5.7	6.0	6.0	3.8	6.1
Neighboring farmers	mean	4.6	4.5	4.8	5.0	4.6	4.0	4.6
Environmental NGOs	mean	3.0	3.0	3.0	4.1	3.0	3.7	2.4
overall trust	mean	4.0	4.1	3.9	4.4	4.2	3.3	4.0
Preference on free-cultivation regime								
Without restriction	% farms	20%	0.0	0.0	0.0	65.5	0.0	42.0
Under regulation like other crops	% farms	36%	0.0	0.0	0.0	89.7	0.0	90.0
Preferences on restrictions								
Minimum distance from other crops	% farms	38%	74.3	57.1	46.7	0.0	9.1	0.0
Use of natural barriers	% farms	30%	52.7	52.4	66.7	0.0	0.0	0.0
Gene-editing labelling	% farms	38%	68.9	66.7	73.3	0.0	0.0	0.0
Tracing gene-edited products	% farms	43%	82.4	66.7	66.7	0.0	9.1	0.0
Mandatory risk assessment	% farms	47%	85.1	85.7	73.3	0.0	18.2	0.0
Preferences on reasons to ban NGT crops								
Consumers do not want them	% farms	3%	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	45.5	0.0
Danger to health and environment	% farms	3%	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	45.5	0.0
Ruin the image of rural economy	% farms	2%	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	36.4	0.0